

Evaluation of PERD: Personalized Emoji Recommendation with Dynamic User Preference

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Introduction to PERD

- Model for predicting appropriate emojis for a social media post
- Also takes historical post of users into account to give user specific predictions
- Was trained on two datasets:
 - Weibo (1.53 million post by 98600 users)
 - Twitter (1.63 million post by 6500 users)
- In total 50 unique emojis (multi-class problem)

PROBLEMS FOUND

1. Inadequate literature review
2. Datasets are not provided → only unspecified sample data
3. Code needed clean up and some bug fixing
4. No information on train-test-validation split
5. Experimental setup partly described (missing information on hardware and library version setup)
6. Performance metrics missing context which set is used as well as runtime evaluation

Achieved Steps

1. Fixed Code
2. Run experiment on subset of example data
3. Create report

Next Steps

1. Format and check report
2. hand-in report and code